

Spectral Analysis by medians

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In this work, we propose a new and simple method for the spectral analysis of a wave signal without using the Fourier transform. This approach may be useful in certain cases and offers some advantages.

The method is based on an iterative algorithm that, at each iteration, attempts to identify the component that best resembles the signal and subtracts it. The process continues until no sufficiently suitable new component can be found.

Therefore, it is necessary to initially specify a set of components to be used, along with their frequencies. The algorithm, in addition to determining the amplitude, is also capable of estimating the phase of each frequency component by adding, for each one, a sine component shifted by 90 degrees.

During each iteration, the algorithm evaluates all components and, for each of them, generates an array by dividing each value of the signal by the corresponding value of the component.

It then calculates the number of negative and positive values in the array, obtaining a coefficient equal to $\max(\text{num_neg}, \text{num_pos})/\text{array_length}$. The higher this value, the greater the similarity between the component and the signal.

At the end of the iteration, the component with the highest coefficient is selected and subtracted from the signal. This component is also stored in the array of final components.

To obtain the multiplicative factor of the component, the algorithm uses the median value (the central element of the array of divisions after sorting it).

Empirical results showed that 0.6 was a suitable minimum coefficient threshold for accepting a component. Here we have the flow diagram:

Further exhaustive testing would be required to more thoroughly validate the algorithm. However, as an example, I provide Python code that generates a signal by

summing three known, phase-shifted sine waves, and then analyzes the signal using the proposed method to retrieve the components, yielding satisfactory results.

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#Python program for Spectral Analysis by medians
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import numpy as np
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt

# Parameters for the simulation (sum/wave)
ts1=0
ts2=1

fs = 1000          # sample frequency (Hz)
t = np.linspace(ts1, ts2, (ts2-ts1)*fs, endpoint=False) # time vector (1
second)

# Parameters for the simulation (signals)
ts1s=0
ts2s=ts2-ts1

fs = 1000          # sample frequency (Hz)
ts = np.linspace(ts1s, ts2s, (ts2s-ts1s)*fs, endpoint=False) # time vector (1
second)

# Parameters for the 3 signals
A1, f1, phi1 = 1.0, 5, 0          # amplitude, frequency, phase
A2, f2, phi2 = 0.5, 15, np.pi/4  # phase in radians
A3, f3, phi3 = 0.8, 30, np.pi/2

# Individual signals
s1 = A1 * np.sin(2 * np.pi * f1 * t + phi1)
s2 = A2 * np.sin(2 * np.pi * f2 * t + phi2)
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s3 = A3 * np.sin(2 * np.pi * f3 * t + phi3)

# Señal compuesta (suma)
suma = s1 + s2 + s3

# Graphics:
plt.figure(figsize=(12, 8))

plt.subplot(4,1,1)
plt.plot(t, s1)
plt.title("Señal 1: seno de {} Hz, fase {} rad".format(f1, phi1))
plt.ylabel("Amplitud")

plt.subplot(4,1,2)
plt.plot(t, s2)
plt.title("Señal 2: seno de {} Hz, fase {} rad".format(f2, phi2))
plt.ylabel("Amplitud")

plt.subplot(4,1,3)
plt.plot(t, s3)
plt.title("Señal 3: seno de {} Hz, fase {} rad".format(f3, phi3))
plt.ylabel("Amplitud")

plt.subplot(4,1,4)
plt.plot(t, suma)
plt.title("Suma de las 3 señales")
plt.xlabel("Tiempo (s)")
plt.ylabel("Amplitud")

# Frequencies from 5 to 30 Hz, step 5
frecuencias = np.arange(5, 31, 5)

componentes=[[ ],[ ]]

for i_f, f in enumerate(frecuencias):

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    for p in [0,1]:
        componentes[p].append(0.0)

componentes = np.array(componentes)

print(componentes)

# Array to store signals
senales = [[],[]]

# Generate senus with phases 0 and 90°
for f in frecuencias:
    s0 = np.sin(2 * np.pi * f * ts + 0)          # phase 0 rad
    s90 = np.sin(2 * np.pi * f * ts + np.pi/2) # phase 90 rad
    senales[0].append(s0)
    senales[1].append(s90)

# Convert list to array (each row is a signal)
senales = np.array(senales)

# Spectral analysis by medians

n=0

while True:

    max_coef=0

    for i_f, f in enumerate(frecuencias):
        for p in [0,1]:

            divs=[]
            num_tot=0

            for i in range((ts2-ts1)*fs):

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        if senales[p,i_f,i]!=0:
            divs.append(suma[i]/senales[p,i_f,i])
            num_tot+=1

num_pos=0
num_neg=0

for i in range(len(divs)):
    if divs[i]>=0:
        num_pos+=1
    else:
        num_neg+=1

coef=max(num_pos,num_neg)/num_tot

divs.sort()

multi=divs[len(divs)//2]

if coef>max_coef:
    max_coef=coef
    max_multi=multi
    max_i_f=i_f
    max_f=f
    max_p=p

if max_coef>=0.6:
    #print(max_coef)
    #print(max_multi)
    #print(max_f)
    #print(max_p)

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suma-=max_multi*senales[max_p,max_i_f]

componentes[max_p,max_i_f]=componentes[max_p,max_i_f]+max_multi

else:
    break

plt.subplot(4,1,4)
plt.plot(t, suma)
plt.title("Suma de las 3 señales y resto de señal después de análisis")
plt.xlabel("Tiempo (s)")
plt.ylabel("Amplitud")

plt.tight_layout()
plt.show()

print(componentes)

print(suma) #To see the rest from wave that lefts after the spectral analysis
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Conclusions:

The proposed algorithm/method offers the advantage of being highly accurate in identifying the amplitudes and phases of the components used to approximate the input signal. Furthermore, by employing the median, it proves to be fairly robust against noise spikes in the signal. Also, it requires little signal length to obtain results.

However, in order to achieve precision, the algorithm requires that all frequencies potentially present in the input signal be specified as components. The greater the number of frequencies in the input that deviate from the defined components, the less accurate the result will be. A possible improvement is to provide a range of components that cover the entire frequency spectrum with enough resolution.

Naturally, the method should be validated with real and more complex samples. Nonetheless, the remaining signal can be easily examined to assess the quality of the approximation.